

Ectopic Pregnancy Concealed by Intrauterine Pseudoembryo: A Case Report on Fallacious Sonographic Findings

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Abstract—

background: Ectopic pregnancy, where a fertilized ovum implants outside the uterine cavity, poses significant risks to maternal health. Literature mentions that the uterine cavity should be empty to diagnose an ectopic pregnancy. This is not the situation always because of Arias- Stella phenomenon.

case presentation: A 26-year-old woman G2P1L1 has come with two months of amenorrhea & pain abdomen. TVS revealed an intrauterine embryo without cardiac activity along with a blood clot. She was posted for D & C for missed abortion. 3 weeks post procedure, patient came back to casualty with pain abdomen & dizziness. Further investigation diagnosed a ruptured ectopic pregnancy. She underwent laparoscopy and left salpingectomy.

results: Histopathological examination post-D&C specimen showed Arias-Stella reaction with decidualized endometrial glands and stroma without chorionic villi. Intraoperative findings during laparoscopy revealed a ruptured left fallopian tube with active bleeding and a pelvic hematoma. Postoperative recovery was uneventful after appropriate surgical and medical interventions.

discussion: The case highlights a rare fallacious sonographic findings, termed "pseudoembryo," where an echogenic focus mimics an embryo, complicating the diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy.

conclusion: Recognition of the "pseudoembryo" sign is vital for accurate diagnosis and management of ectopic pregnancies. Awareness of this potential pitfall can prevent misdiagnosis and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords— Ectopic Pregnancy, Intrauterine Echogenic Focus, Pseudogestational sac, Pseudoembryo, Transvaginal Ultrasonography.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ectopic pregnancy occurs when a fertilized ovum implants outside the uterine cavity, most commonly in the fallopian tube, posing significant maternal health risks. A pseudogestational sac is an intrauterine fluid collection without a yolk sac or embryo,

may indicate either an ectopic pregnancy or an early intrauterine pregnancy [1]. Key ultrasound markers, such as the double decidual and intradecidual signs, may be absent in such cases [2].

Timely diagnosis is crucial, as ectopic pregnancies can lead to life-threatening complications, including rupture and hemorrhagic shock [3]. Symptoms range from pelvic pain and vaginal bleeding to signs of hypovolemic shock. The Arias-Stella reaction, a histological change mimicking early pregnancy, can be present in ectopic pregnancy, necessitating careful interpretation of findings [4].

Transvaginal ultrasonography (TVS) is the primary diagnostic tool, offering high-resolution imaging of pelvic structures [5]. However, TVS may yield ambiguous results, such as an intrauterine echogenic focus within a fluid-filled endometrial cavity, leading to diagnostic uncertainty [6]. These results may be the consequences of pronounced Arias- Stella reaction, mimicking a pseudogestational sac & embryo, are infrequent in occurrence. This case study delves into a complex clinical scenario where intrauterine echogenic focus identified within a fluid-filled endometrial cavity, findings initially suggested an intrauterine pregnancy, but further evaluation confirmed an ectopic pregnancy.

II. CASE PRESENTATION

A 26-year-old woman (G2P1L1) came to the labor room with complaints of lower abdominal pain for 2 days and a history of two months of amenorrhea & positive urine pregnancy test. She had no vaginal bleeding. She had irregular menstrual cycles, ranging from 30 to 45 days, with moderate flow and no dysmenorrhea. As per her last menstrual period, she was 8 weeks 4 days. She was married for five years & she had delivered a healthy male baby via emergency cesarean section for fetal distress. She had no significant medical or surgical history.

On examination, her vital signs were stable. The abdomen was soft, with a Pfannenstiel scar from the previous cesarean, which was non-tender on palpation.

A transvaginal ultrasound (TVS) revealed following findings. There was a hyperechoic irregular focus in endometrial cavity measuring 2.5 x 2.7cms, suggestive of an intrauterine clot(Figure 1).There was a circular structure with bright rim measuring 2.6mm resembling yolk sac(Figure 2). There was an elongated focal thickening measuring 11.3mm resembling 7 weeks embryo without cardiac activity(Figure 3). There was no obvious mass or fluid collection in adnexa (Figures 4,5) & pouch of Douglas. These findings were reported as missed abortion with intrauterine hematoma & patient was posted for dilatation &curettage. Post procedure the pain subsided & there was minimal vaginal bleeding. She was discharged from hospital after 2 days of D &

C. Though patient was advised for follow up after 15 days, she did not come as she had no complaints. Post discharge patient had minimal bleeding for 12 days without any pain abdomen.

Representation (3 weeks post discharge)- Three weeks post-discharge, the patient presented to the casualty with lower abdominal pain that began the previous evening, described as pricking in nature. She also experienced dizziness and a brief loss of consciousness but had no vaginal bleeding.

On examination, her vital signs remained stable, but her abdomen was distended with suprapubic tenderness and guarding. Per vaginal examination revealed bilateral forniceal tenderness.

A transabdominal ultrasound showed an ill-defined mixed echogenic area adjacent to the uterus, extending into the pouch of Douglas (POD), suggestive of a pelvic hematoma. The uterus was anteverted with an endometrial thickness of 7 mm. Free fluid in the peritoneal cavity was also noted, likely indicating hemoperitoneum or ascites.

MRI imaging was done to exclude uterine perforation as she had undergone D & C 3 weeks back. It revealed an ill-defined heterogeneous area adjacent to the uterus, extending into the POD, consistent with a pelvic hematoma. A moderate amount of free fluid with internal echoes was seen in the peritoneal cavity, suggesting hemoperitoneum or ascites. Additionally, mild left pleural effusion and hepatomegaly with fatty infiltration were observed. Her haemoglobin level was 9.1 g/dL. β -hCG levels were elevated at 11891 mIU/mL, indicating persistent trophoblastic activity. Histopathological report of the previous D&C sample was analysed & it revealed an Arias-Stella reaction with decidualized endometrial glands and stroma. No chorionic villi were identified. This report further led us to the diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy which was in the nascent stage at the time of dilatation & curettage.

She was posted for emergency laparoscopy under general anaesthesia. Intraoperative findings revealed a ruptured ectopic pregnancy in the ampullary portion of the left fallopian tube, measuring 3 × 3 cm. Active bleeding was noted at the rupture site, along with 200 grams of clotted blood in the hemoperitoneum. Left salpingectomy was done & peritoneal wash was given. A drain was placed in the pouch of Douglas (POD) to ensure adequate drainage. Haemostasis was achieved & port closures done. Patient withstood procedure well.

After surgery, the patient received two units of packed cell volume (PCV) to correct anaemia. Intravenous antibiotics were initiated, later transitioned to oral antibiotics. There was no significant collection in the drain & it was removed on post

operative day 2. Histopathological report post salpingectomy sample was collected & it revealed features consistent with ruptured ectopic. The patient recovered well and was discharged on the fourth postoperative day.

III. DISCUSSION

Ectopic pregnancy is a diagnosis that is quite challenging to make. It has been estimated that 40% of ectopic pregnancies go undiagnosed on initial presentation.[12] Ectopic pregnancy is also a very difficult condition to identify based on history and physical examination, with both the history and physical examination features being neither sensitive nor specific for the diagnosis. Data suggests that even experienced gynecologists are unable to detect more than half of the masses created by ectopic pregnancy on physical examination. [13] Barnhart and colleagues reported that an empty uterus with a serum b-hCG concentration >1500 mIU/ml was 100 percent accurate in excluding a live uterine pregnancy.[14] But the uterine cavity with ectopic pregnancy is not empty always. Previous literature on ectopic pregnancies has extensively discussed the occurrence of pseudogestational sacs. While an article by Catherine H. P. et al says, in a woman with positive human chorionic gonadotropin results and no extraovarian adnexal mass, the ultrasound finding of an intrauterine saclike structure is virtually certain to be a gestational sac. Concepts introduced 30 to 40 years ago when ultrasound equipment had far lower resolution than currently, including a DDS, an IDS, and a pseudogestational sac, have no role today in assessing early pregnancy. [15]

According to studies, up to 1 in 10 ectopic pregnancies may present with a pseudogestational sac, which is a fluid-filled collection within the endometrial cavity that can be mistaken for a true gestational sac[7-9]. These sacs are typically devoid of any embryonic structures and are considered a hallmark of ectopic pregnancies. For instance, an article by Nyberg et al. discusses the sonographic appearances of ectopic pregnancies, highlighting the importance of differentiating between true intrauterine gestational sacs and pseudogestational sacs. [10] Study by Lee R et al. discusses various atypical sonographic findings in ectopic pregnancies but does not report any cases involving echogenic structures mimicking embryos within pseudogestational sacs.[11] This underscores the uniqueness of our case and the need for heightened awareness among clinicians.

The "pseudoembryo" sign described in our case study adds to previous literature. Case reports have been less on echogenic focal blood clot within the endometrial canal, which mimics an embryo. This finding is particularly significant because it can lead to the misinterpretation of a pseudogestational sac as a normal intrauterine pregnancy, thereby complicating the diagnosis and management of ectopic pregnancies.

These decidual changes observed with ectopic pregnancy are probably due to Arias- Stella phenomenon. In 1954, Arias-Stella, a Peruvian pathologist, described certain changes in the glandular part of the endometrium associated with the presence of

chorionic tissues and due to the hormonal influence of the chorionic tissues. He postulated that these atypical changes in the endometrium were due to the "unique stimulation" of increased oestrogen and progesterone occasioned by the presence of the chorionic tissue.[16]

Sonologists need to be alert when a gestational sac is located in the endometrial cavity instead of its eccentric location in the endometrial walls, or a normal yolk sac (a round structure with dark center & bright rim) & a fetal pole (Focal oval thickening on the margin of yolk sac) are not seen, or a blood clot is seen. Visualisation of adnexa is imperative although early ectopic pregnancies cannot be visualised on transvaginal ultrasound, evident in our case. Ectopic pregnancies, in such cases can be confirmed by beta- hCG trend in 48 hours or histopathological examination of curettage sample post procedure. The hCG levels may be increasing or decreasing. In both case, serial monitoring to be continued till they reach discriminatory levels when ultrasound is to be repeated, or becomes undetectable. The curretage sample showing Arias- stella reaction or absence of chorionic villi should make us vigilant about concealed ectopic pregnancy.

A. Figures and Tables

Fig. 1 Intrauterine clot during first admission

Fig.2.Yolk sac at first admission

Fig. 2 Elongated focal thickening resembling fetal pole during first admission.

Fig. 4 Right adnexa during first admission.

Fig. 5 Left adnexa during first admission.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This case study expands the understanding of ectopic pregnancy by emphasizing the "pseudoembryo" sign. Clinicians must be aware of this diagnostic pitfall to prevent misinterpretation and improve patient outcomes through accurate early diagnosis and intervention.

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